

The Students' Perception towards the Online Learning Implementation of Hair Trimming Course

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ABSTRACT: Online learning for Hair Trimming Course using Whatsapp, Zoom, and Elearning2unp applications is conducted by creating a class group and learning interaction using chat features and uploading material files, but the implementation is still not maximal. This study aimed at 1) knowing the students' perceptions about online learning facilities in hair trimming course, 2) knowing the students' perceptions about the students' capacity in using online learning facilities in hair trimming course, 3) knowing the students' perceptions of online learning activities in hair trimming course, and 4) knowing the students' perception of online learning implementation in hair trimming course. This was a descriptive study using a quantitative approach. The variable was single. The population was the students majoring in the Department of Makeup and Beauty, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality, Universitas Negeri Padang batch 2019 by using the probability sampling technique. This study used primary data. The data collection technique was in the form of questionnaires or structured questionnaires. The instrument was a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The tests applied to the instrument were the validity test and reliability test. The data analysis technique used a descriptive statistical analysis. Based on the result of the study, it can conclude that the majority of the students batch 2019 have a less positive perception towards the implementation of online learning in the hair trimming course. This can be seen from the online learning facilities showing 12.5% (strongly positive), 17.9% (positive), 59% (less positive), and 10.3% (negative). For the educators' and the students' capacity in using the online learning facilities, the result is 12.8% (strongly positive), 10.3% (positive), 64.1% (less positive), and 12.8% (negative). Meanwhile, the result for the online learning activities is 7.7% (strongly positive), 46.2% (positive), 33.3% (less positive), and 12.8% (negative). Consequently, overall, the students' perception against the implementation of online learning in the hair trimming course is categorized as less positive. The students are suggested to maximize the use of online learning facilities in the hair trimming course to achieve a better outcome.

KEYWORDS: Students' Perception, Online Learning, Hair Trimming

INTRODUCTION

Education in Indonesia plays a big role in creating good quality generations. In general, education is the learning process from someone to other people to improve knowledge and skills. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic attacking Indonesia, educational activities are disrupted. The problem is that this transmission of this pandemic disease is categorized fast and fatal, which the method for mitigation is by decreasing the transmission from someone to other people. Hence, the special policy is established by both the central government and the local government aiming at stopping the COVID-19 transmission and it is known as physical distancing.

Based on the circular letter by the rector, the theoretical lecturing in UNP for the semester from January to June 2021 is still conducted online until the end of the semester, while the practical course can be conducted offline by fulfilling several requirements that have been established.

The department of make-up and beauty is one of the departments in the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality in Universitas Negeri Padang, in that the course consists of theory and practice. Based on the preliminary survey on March 22, 2021, to 15 students of the Department of Make-up and Beauty about the online learning system, especially for the Hair Trimming course, that had been conducted using *WhatsApp*, *Zoom*, and *Elearning2unp* applications, showed that the learning was conducted by creating a class group and learning interaction using chat features and uploading teaching materials. This learning is included in the synchronous online learning. Nevertheless, from the students' opinions against the online learning implementation, it was not maximal yet. This can be seen from the online learning facilities, such as unstable Internet networks, insufficient Internet quota, some students who have no laptop, ineffective teaching materials, and insufficient learning media. Furthermore, the facilities provided by the lecturers and the institution were not used maximally, such as there were still some students who used the students' internet quota for opening

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social media, some students who did not use the tutorial videos provided the lecturers to practice the hair trimming. E-learning is still made as the facility to upload and download the lecturing materials, a face-to-face meeting is rarely conducted using zoom or Google meet application or the similar application, and the students have difficulties in understanding and doing many assignments given by the lecturers so that the online learning activities are not effective.

It is in line with the result of the study by Purwanto, et al. (2020) that the obstacle faced by the students is that the students are demanded to have online learning without an adequate facility. Facilities and infrastructures are required for helping the success of the learning process, such as smartphones, computers, and laptops, and facilitating the students in learning. The impact faced by the parents is that the expense of purchasing the Internet quota since one of the required online learning facilities is the Internet network. The next impact felt by the teachers is that they were not fully capable of using the Internet technology or social media as the learning facility.

The result of the study by Handarini & Wu1andari (2020) showed that the challenge in conducting online learning was adequate facilities, such as smartphones, computers, laptops, and Internet connection. Meanwhile, the result of the study by Suryaman, et al. (2020), stated that some obstacles faced by the students and the lecturers in online learning were lacking technology mastery and high expense for Internet quota.

METHODS

This study was a descriptive study using a quantitative approach. This study was conducted in the Department of Make-up and Beauty, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality, UNP. The study was conducted from April to May 2021. This study used a single variable. The population of this study was the students of the Department of Make-up and Beauty, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality, UNP batch 2019 by using the probability sampling technique. It used primary data. The data collection technique was using a questionnaire or structured questionnaires. The instrument was a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The tests applied to the research instrument were the validity test and reliability test. The data analysis technique in this study was statistical descriptive analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

1. The Research Result Description

a. The students' perception in the online learning implementation is based on the following indicators:

1) Online Learning Facilities

The data for online learning facilities consisted of 17 statements. Based on the data processing, it was obtained a maximum score of = 61, a minimum score of 38, an average score of 49.47, and a standard deviation (SD) of 38.

Table 1. The Frequency Distribution of Online Learning Facilities

No.	Category	Interval Score	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Positive	$X > 54$	5	12.5%
2	Positive	$50 < X \leq 54$	7	17.9%
3	Less Positive	$45 < X \leq 50$	23	59%
4	Negative	$X \leq 45$	4	10.3%
Total			39	100%

Figure 1. The Pie Chart for the Frequency of Online Learning Facilities

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Consequently, The students' perception of online learning implementation in the hair trimming course was analyzed from the online learning facilities with an average score for the perception of 49.74 categorized as less positive.

2) The students' capacity in using the online learning facilities

The data from the students' capacity in using online learning facilities consisted of 12 question items. Based on the data processing, it obtained a maximum score of 44, a minimum score of 25, an average score of 34.72, and a standard deviation (SD) of 3.980.

Table 2. The Frequency Distribution of the Students' Capacity in Using Online Learning Facilities

No.	Category	Interval Score	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Positive	$X > 39$	5	12.8%
2	Positive	$35 < X \leq 39$	4	10.3%
3	Less Positive	$31 < X \leq 35$	25	64.1%
4	Negative	$X \leq 31$	5	12.8%
Total			39	100%

Figure 2. The Pie Chart for the Frequency of the Students' Capacity in Using Online Learning Facilities

Thus, the students' perception against online learning implementation was analyzed from the students' capacity in using online learning facilities with an average score of 34.72 was categorized as less positive.

3) Online Learning Activities

The data from the online learning activities consisted of 16 question items. Based on the data processing obtained a maximum score of 57, a minimum score of 30, an average score of 45.08, and a standard deviation (SD) of 5.460.

Table 3. The Frequency Distribution of Online Learning Activities

No.	Category	Interval Score	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Positive	$X > 51$	3	7.7%
2	Positive	$45 < X \leq 51$	18	46.2%
3	Less Positive	$40 < X \leq 45$	13	33.3%
4	Negative	$X \leq 40$	5	12.8%
Total			39	100%

Figure 3. The Pie Chart for the Frequency of Online Learning Activities

Hence, the students' perception against online learning implementation in the hair trimming course was analyzed from the online learning activities with an average score for the perception of 45.08 that was categorized as positive.

b. The students' perception of online learning implementation in the hair trimming course

Based on the result of the data processing, it was obtained a maximum score of 154, a minimum score of 94, an average score of 129, and a standard deviation of 12.628.

Table 4. The Frequency Distribution of the Students' Perception of Online Learning Implementation in the Hair Trimming Course

No.	Category	Interval Score	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Positive	$X > 142$	6	15.4%
2	Positive	$129 < X \leq 142$	11	28.2%
3	Less Positive	$116 < X \leq 129$	18	46.2%
4	Negative	$X \leq 116$	4	10.3%
Total			39	100 %

Figure 4. The Pie Chart for the Frequency of the Students' Perception of the Online Learning Implementation of Hair Trimming Course

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Thus, the majority of the students' perception of the online learning implementation of hair trimming course was less positive with 18 students in total or 46.2%.

DISCUSSION

From the result of the study, the total for the online learning facilities was 23 students (59%) in the less positive category; the total for the students' capacity in using online learning facilities in the less positive category reached 25 students (64.1%), and the total for the online learning activities in the less positive category reached 13 students (33.3%). This shows that the most dominant perception by the students is less positive in the aspect of students' capacity in using online learning facilities. Therefore, the students are expected to maximize the online learning facilities, such as using the website, internet quota, learning media, @wifi.id, and the Internet in the online learning process in the hair trimming course.

Moreover, the aspect of online learning facilities is vital to be noticed since the students' perception towards the aspect is less positive. It aims to make the online teaching and learning process in the hair trimming course more maximal.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the study in the students of the Department of Make-up and Beauty, it can conclude that the majority of the students in batch 2019 have a less positive perception towards the online learning implementation of hair trimming course. It can be seen that the percentage for the online learning facilities is 12.5% (strongly positive), 17.9% (positive), 59% (less positive), and 10.3% (negative). The percentage for the students' capacity in using the online learning facilities is 12.8% (strongly positive), 10.3% (positive), 64.1% (less positive), and 12.8% (negative). Meanwhile, the percentage for the online learning activities is 7.7% (strongly positive), 46.2% (positive), 33.3% (less positive), and 12.8% (negative). Consequently, the overall students' perception of online learning implementation in the hair trimming course is categorized as less positive.

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